

Spectrophotometric microdetermination of gadolinium(III) and terbium(III) with xylenol orange in presence of cationic cetylpyridinium bromide as a surfactant

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Abstract : Xylenol orange (XO) has been reported earlier to form violet colored binary complexes with several lanthanides and used for the determination of several metal ions. The addition of cationic surfactant, cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB) to the colored solution of xylenol orange resulted into discoloration at specific pH values which is due to the interaction of anionic XO with cationic CPB. The addition of specific metal ions to this decolorized solution resulted into formation of deeply colored water soluble stable ternary complexes with a large bathochromic shift of 42 nm with increase in absorbance at shifted wavelength. Stoichiometric composition of 1 : 2 : 4 (e.g. Gd^{III}-XO-CPB) has been observed by Job's method of continuous variation. The values of log *K* for both binary and ternary complexes have been calculated. The ternary complexes were formed in wider pH range with increase in stability and exhibited absorption maxima at 612 nm for both the metal ions under study. Various analytical parameters like order of addition of reactants, effect of time and temperature, effect of reagent concentration, Beer's law, photometric ranges, Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity have also been calculated and compared. The effects of interfering ions on determination of both the metal ions were studied. A simple, rapid and highly sensitive method for the determination of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} with xylenol orange is proposed.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, xylenol orange (XO), cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB), gadolinium (Gd), terbium (Tb).

Introduction

Organic reagents play an important role in analytical and complexation chemistry of lanthanides for its microdetermination. With increase in demand for the more sensitive reagents, attempts have been made in the recent past for more intensification of color of binary complex to increase the sensitivity of reagents by using third component like surfactant by converting binary complex to multicomponent ternary complexes at very low concentration.

Lanthanides are widely used for various purposes in modern science and technology and the researchers have attracted their attention on its microdetermination. Due to high absorption property of neutrons, gadolinium is used for shielding in neutron radiography and in nuclear

reactors. It is used in iron, chromium and in some alloys to increase their resistance to oxidation at high temperatures. In the medical realm, solutions of gadolinium compounds are used as intravenous contrasts to enhance images in patients undergoing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Terbium oxide is used in green phosphors in fluorescent lamps and color TV tubes. It is also used as a dopant in calcium fluoride, calcium tungstate and strontium molybdate which are used in solid-state devices. It can be used with ZrO₂ as a crystal stabilizer in high temperature fuel cells. Lanthanum and yttrium are used in high technology applications, such as in superconductors, supermagnets, laser and alloys¹.

Spectrophotometric microdetermination of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with chrome azurol-S and pyrogallol red in presence

of cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide was reported by Upase and coworkers^{2,3}. Belsare *et al.* has reported the spectrophotometric study of ternary complex of some rare earths with bromopyrogallol red in presence of cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide for microdetermination of metal ions⁴. Dhepe *et al.*⁵ has studied spectrophotometric determination of some lanthanide metal ions with eriochrome cyanine R in presence of cetylpyridinium bromide. Spectrophotometric determination of thorium, lanthanum and yttrium in some geological and environmental samples was carried by Abdallah *et al.* using eriochrome cyanine R in presence of Triton X-100 and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide⁶. The surfactant cetylpyridinium bromide sensitized analytical reaction of cerium(IV) with some triphenylformazan derivatives was studied by Ahmed and his coworkers⁷. Determination of trace amount of ruthenium(III) by the spectrophotometric method with rhodamine B in micellar medium cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was studied by Keyvanfar⁸. Samarium(III) was determined spectrophotometrically by Soylak using chrome azurol-S in presence of cetylpyridinium chloride⁹. Some of the rare earth elements with chromeazurol S in presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and Triton X-100 were determined spectrophotometrically by Preisler¹⁰.

A spectrophotometric reagent, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-*p*-hydroxybenzoic hydrazone as was used for the determination of lanthanum(III) in presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide by Chowdary¹¹. Li-xin and coworkers have studied the ternary interaction of naphthochrome green with cetyltrimethylammonium bromide with some trivalent rare earths like yttrium, dysprosium, erbium and europium using the microsurface adsorption-spectral correction technique¹². Cerium subgroup rare earths in nickel-base alloys in presence of yttrium with *p*-acetylchlorophosphonazo and mixed surfactants were determined spectrophotometrically by Chung-Gin Hsu *et al.*¹³. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was used in the solvent extraction of lanthanide complexes of bromopyrogallol red and microdetermination of these complexes were studied spectrophotometrically by Roy and Sangal¹⁴. Walash and coworkers have determined ciclopirox olamine via ternary complex with terbium(III) and EDTA by spectrofluorimetric method¹⁵. The solution studies of ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes of

europium, gadolinium, and terbium(III) with benzoic acid/its derivatives and uracil/its halo derivatives in dioxane-water (30 : 70 v/v) medium (ionic strength $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaNO}_3$) have been performed by Shalu Tyagi *et al.*¹⁶.

Amin has reported the method based on luminescence sensitization of terbium(III) by formation of ternary complex with IB in the presence of tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide and Tween-20 as surfactant¹⁷. Cationic surfactants such as cetylpyridinium bromide sensitize the color reaction of niobium(V) with 1-(2-benzothiazolylazo)-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (**1a**), 5-(benzothiazolylazo)-2,5-naphthalenediol (**1b**), 5-(2-benzothiazolylazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (**1c**) and 4-(2-benzothiazolylazo)-2,2-biphenyldiol (**1d**) reagents¹⁸. Lanthanum, holmium and manganese in synthetic ceramics, $(\text{La}_{(0.8-x)}\text{Ho}_x\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_3)$ were determined spectrophotometrically by using chromogenic agent 5-Br-PADAP [2-(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)-5-diethylamino-phenol] and Triton X-100 as a surfactant by Ferreyra and coworkers¹⁹.

The detail and systematic study of color reactions and complex formation of xylenol orange (XO) with gadolinium(III) and terbium(III) in presence of micelle forming cationic surfactant cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB) have not been reported so far. Considering the increasing demand of more sensitive reagents, the present study has been planned for sensitization of xylenol orange by using micelle forming cationic surfactant CPB for the microdetermination of gadolinium(III) and terbium(III) which primarily decides the usefulness and its importance for determination of metal ions. The results of experiments carried out with XO in presence of CPB and its interaction with Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} along with its analytical applications have been discussed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade purity. XO supplied by Sigma Chemical Company and CPB by Aldrich Chemical Company was used. The purity of CPB was tested by argentometric titration for determination of bromide ion content²⁰. Both the metal ions used as their oxides and were supplied by Indian Rare Earth Ltd., India, of 99.99% purity. The stock solutions of XO of $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ and CPB of $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$ strength were prepared. The metal ion solution of $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ strength

was prepared by dissolving respective oxides in minimum quantity of analytical grade hydrochloric acid which was standardized by precipitating metal ions as their oxalates and were estimated volumetrically by using bromopyrogallol red as a complexometric indicator. All subsequent dilutions of desired concentration were made by using double distilled water.

The CPB solution was first added to XO solution and was kept for half an hour. The metal ion solution was then added to this solution and again kept for half an hour to reach complete equilibrium. This order of mixing of solutions was maintained throughout the work. All the absorption measurements were made by using Systronics Visiscan-167 model spectrophotometer with matched glass cells of 10 mm light path working on its current supply (220 V) device. The pH adjustment was done using Elico Model LI-10 pH meter with glass and calomel electrode assembly and checked frequently with buffer solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax. The pH of solution was adjusted using hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions of suitable concentration.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra of XO :

The spectral studies of XO have been carried out in the pH range 1.0 to 10.0 in visible region from 400 to 700 nm in absence (Fig. 1) and presence of CPB (Fig. 2). The reagent shows different absorption maxima at different pH values. Deeply colored solution of XO brings about notable color change by the addition of small amount of CPB. The various wavelength of XO at different pH values have been summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of XO.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of XO in presence of CPB.

Table 1. λ_{\max} of XO in absence and presence of CPB

XO		XO + CPB	
pH	λ_{\max}	pH	λ_{\max}
1.0	446	1.0	456
2.0	450	2.0	452
3.0	426	3.0	444
3.5	450	3.5	442
4.0-7.0	452	4.0-7.0	448
7.5-10.0	618	7.5-10.0	626

From the spectral studies, it has been observed that the maximum decolorizing effect of XO takes place at pH 6.0 in acidic medium and at pH 9.0 in alkaline medium in presence of CPB. It has been observed that absorbance values of XO decreases in presence of CPB. However decrease in absorbance values of XO in the acidic range is somewhat less as compared to basic medium.

The absorption spectra of XO solution show characteristic λ_{\max} at 452 nm in less acidic and alkaline medium while λ_{\max} at 450 nm in more acidic medium. On addition of CPB in more acidic medium, the absorbance decreases with appearance of new peak at 460 nm causing color change from red to light red and in more diluted solution to almost colorless. This color change has been achieved in acidic medium due to early dissociation of protons of XO in presence of CPB. This decolorization might be attributed to the interaction between anionic dye and cationic surfactant.

Study of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} complexes of XO in absence and presence of CPB :

The wavelengths of maximum absorption of XO and its complexes with Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} in absence and presence of CPB in pH range 3.0 to 9.0 are recorded in Table 2. For studying the nature of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} complexes in absence and presence of CPB, the comparative absorption spectra of XO have been plotted for Gd^{III} at pH 6.2 in Fig. 3 and for Tb^{III} at pH 6.1 in Fig. 4.

The precipitation of both the metal ions under study has occurred above pH 6.0 in absence of CPB. However, in presence of CPB, the precipitation of both ternary metal complexes has not observed upto pH 9.0.

Strong complexation in presence of CPB with a large bathochromic shift of ternary complexes has been observed which appeared to be convenient to study the analytical applications further. As the modified XO reagent has considerable absorbance value at the λ_{\max} 612 nm of

Table 2. Absorbance maxima (nm) of XO and its metal complexes in absence and presence of CPB at different pH values

System	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0	7.5	8.0	8.5	9.0
XO	426	450	452	450	452	452	452	452	452	618	618	618	618
XO + CPB	442	442	448	448	448	448	448	448	448	626	626	626	626
XO + Gd ^{III}	465	540	546	570	570	570	570	-	-	-	-	-	-
XO + CPB + Gd ^{III}	440	552	560	574	612	612	612	612	612	620	620	620	620
XO + Tb ^{III}	450	542	544	570	570	570	570	-	-	-	-	-	-
XO + CPB + Tb ^{III}	438	548	552	580	612	612	612	612	612	620	620	620	620

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of XO at pH 6.2 for Gd^{III}.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of XO at pH 6.1 for Tb^{III}.

Study of binary and ternary complexes of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} :

Figs. 3 and 4 show the comparative absorption spectra of XO by curve A showing λ_{\max} 452 nm, curve B is the absorption spectra of XO in presence of CPB with λ_{\max} 448 nm, curve C indicates the absorption spectra of binary complex i.e. XO and metal ion with λ_{\max} 570 nm and curve D is the absorption spectra of ternary complex i.e. XO, CPB and metal ion with λ_{\max} 612 nm indicating formation of strong ternary complex showing a bathochromic shift of 42 nm.

both the ternary complexes in acidic range and hence further studies have been made at pH 6.2 and at pH 6.1 for Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} respectively where maximum difference in absorbance between the reagent and ternary complex is observed. The interfering hydrolysis of polyvalent metal ions in the weakly acidic medium has been suppressed due to increase in stability of the complexes in presence of CPB.

Effect of pH :

Figs. 5 and 6 represent variation of λ_{\max} with pH in which curve A indicates that λ_{\max} of XO increases from

Fig. 5. Variation of absorption maxima with pH for Gd^{III}.

Fig. 6. Variation of absorption maxima with pH for Tb^{III}.

pH 1.0–2.0 however decreases at pH 3.0 and it remains constant (λ_{\max} 452 nm) in pH range 4.0–7.0 and again remains constant (λ_{\max} 618 nm) in pH range 7.5–10.0. Curve B indicates that λ_{\max} of XO in presence of CPB decreases from pH 1.0–3.5 and it remains constant (λ_{\max} 448 nm) in pH range 4.0–7.0 and also remains constant

(λ_{\max} 626 nm) in pH range 7.5–10.0. It has been found that curve C shows λ_{\max} 570 nm of binary Gd^{III} complex and remains constant in pH range 4.5 to 6.2 in Fig. 5 and λ_{\max} 570 nm of binary Tb^{III} complex remains constant in pH range 4.5 to 6.4 in Fig. 6. Curve D indicates λ_{\max} 612 nm of ternary Gd^{III} complex which remains constant in pH range 5.0 to 7.0 in Fig. 5. And λ_{\max} 612 nm of ternary Tb^{III} complex remains constant in pH range 5.0 to 7.0 in Fig. 6 in presence of CPB indicating pH range of stability of complex formation. The optimum pH range of stability was found to be 5.8 to 6.2 for Gd^{III} and 6.0 to 6.4 for Tb^{III} in absence; and 5.7 to 6.4 for both metals under study in presence of CPB, where the absorbance remains nearly constant at λ_{\max} 612 nm for complexes of both the metal ions. Thus, ternary complexation takes place in wider pH range as compared to binary complexes. The values of λ_{\max} and bathochromic shifts of both the metal ions under study are given in Table 3.

The variation of the absorbances with change in pH of binary and ternary complexes of Gd^{III} in absence at λ_{\max} 570 nm and in presence of CPB at λ_{\max} 612 nm has been represented by curve C and D in Figs. 7 and 8 respectively. Thus pH range of stability for Gd^{III} is 5.8–6.2 in absence and 5.7–6.2 in presence of CPB where absorbance remains constant. However, pH range of stability for Tb^{III} is 5.8–6.0 in absence and 5.7–6.2 in presence of CPB have been observed where absorbance remains constant. The values of pH range of stability of both the metal ions under study are given in Table 4.

Study of XO-CPB interaction and formation of binary and ternary complexes :

(a) Study of XO-CPB interaction :

The various proton dissociation steps of XO are of great importance for their application as spectrophotometric reagent. There are total nine acid dissociation con-

Table 3. Absorbance maximum and bathochromic shift of complexes of XO in absence and presence of CPB

Lanthanide complexes	λ_{\max} of XO (nm)	λ_{\max} of complexes (nm)	Bathochromic shift as compared to reagent (nm)	Bathochromic shift between binary and ternary complex (nm)
Gd ^{III}	A-452	A-570	A-118	42
	P-448	P-612	P-164	
Tb ^{III}	A-452	A-570	A-118	42
	P-448	P-612	P-164	

A – Absence and B – Presence of CPB.

Fig. 7. Variation of absorbance at constant absorption maxima with pH for binary and ternary complex of Gd^{III} with XO.

Fig. 8. Variation of absorbance at constant absorption maxima with pH for binary and ternary complex of Tb^{III} with XO.

Table 4. pH range of stability of metal complexes of XO in absence and presence of CPB

Lanthanide	λ_{max} of complexes (nm)	pH range of stability of constant wavelength (nm)	pH range of stability of constant absorbance
Gd ^{III}	A-570	A-4.5 – 6.2	A-5.8 – 6.2
	P-612	P-5.0 – 7.0	P-5.7 – 6.4
Tb ^{III}	A-570	A-4.5 – 6.4	A-6.0 – 6.4
	P-612	P-5.0 – 7.0	P-5.7 – 6.4

A – Absence and B – Presence of CPB.

stants corresponding to the dissociation of nine protons in XO. The constant $K_{a,9}$ and $K_{a,8}$ correspond to the dissociation of two phenolic groups. The phenolic proton forms the hydrogen bridge bond with the nitrogen of the tertiary amino group. The four constants i.e. $K_{a,7}$ to $K_{a,4}$

correspond to the dissociation of the four carboxylic groups. The dissociation related to $K_{a,7}$ is mostly responsible for the color change occurring in alkaline media which changes from yellow to red violet. The constant $K_{a,3}$ and $K_{a,2}$ are related to the dissociation of the protonated tertiary amino groups. The color change taking place in the acidic medium is due to the equilibrium corresponding to the constant $K_{a,2}$ which changes from red to yellow. The last constant $K_{a,1}$ which probably related to the deprotonation of the sulphonate group. The various dissociation steps of XO show marked differences in their color characteristics. The dependence of the bathochromic maxima with the changes in pH of an aqueous solution of XO is closely related to the feasibility of using XO as a spectrophotometric reagent for metal ions as complex formation is also accompanied by bathochromic shift, which is restricted in the pH range 0.00 to 6.0 due to protonization and deprotonization. The cationic surfactant play an important role before complexation with metal ion to form binary dye-surfactant association as reported in Scheme 1. Addition of metal ion to this solution results in the formation of ternary complex as reported in Scheme 2.

Stoichiometric composition of XO-CPB complex has been derived by varying the concentration of CPB on absorbance of XO in acidic medium at pH 6.0 with λ_{max} 452 nm and in alkaline medium at pH 9.0 with λ_{max} 618 nm where the maximum decolorizing effect is observed as shown in Figs. 9 and 10 respectively. Three different concentrations of XO i.e. $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, $2.7 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $2.33 \times 10^{-5} M$ have been selected and shown by curve A, B and C respectively.

The intersection of first descending portion and second long horizontal portion of curves clearly indicates that the maximum decolorizing effect is reached at the minimal XO-CPB ratio of 1 : 2 or when this point is reached the absorbance of XO remains unaltered even on addition of ten times of CPB. This indicate that the interaction is ionic as the anionic XO interacts with cationic surfactant resulting into the formation of dye-surfactant association which may be considered as “[XO(CPB)₂]” so called complex at the pH of study. The formation of the species formed by ionic interaction may be represented as shown in Scheme 1 and by omitting charges as follows^{21,22}.

Scheme 1. Formation of XO-CPB association (dye-surfactant complex).

Scheme 2. Formation of ternary complexes with metal ion in presence of CPB.

(b) Study of formation of binary and ternary complexes :

The stoichiometric composition of both the metal ions and XO in absence (Figs. 11 and 13) and presence (Figs. 12 and 14) of ten times concentration of CPB have been found to be 1 : 2 at pH 6.0. It has been observed that XO reagent at pH 6.0 and pH 9.0 exist as [XO(CPB)₂] as two

CPB ions are associated with XO as discussed earlier and therefore, the composition of complexes in presence of CPB may be expressed as M[XO(CPB)₂]₂ for both the metal complexes²³. The composition of the complex was studied by the Job's method of continuous variation²⁴. The formation of complexes may therefore be expressed by an equation (omitting charges) as follows.

Fig. 9. Effect of CPB on XO at pH 6.0 and λ_{\max} 452 nm.

Fig. 10. Effect of CPB on XO at pH 9.0 and λ_{\max} 618 nm.

The values of $\log K$ evaluated by Job's method are shown in Table 5 which indicate that the ternary complexes are more stabilized.

(c) Evaluation of stability constant :

Values of K in absence and presence of CPB can be calculated by using following equation. Now considering reaction where 1 : 2 complex is formed then,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad (i)$$

Fig. 11. Curves of Job's method of binary complex show composition of Gd : XO as 1 : 2 at pH 6.2 and λ_{\max} 568 nm.

Fig. 12. Curves of Job's method of ternary complex show composition of Gd : XO : CPB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 6.2 and λ_{\max} 608 nm.

Taking two concentrations a_1, b_1 and a_2, b_2 having the same absorbance i.e. the same value of 'x' we have,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2}$$

Solving the above equation,

or

$$4x^2 [(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)] + x [b_2^2 - b_1^2 + 4(a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)] + [a_1b_1^2 - a_2b_2^2] = 0 \quad (ii)$$

And the value of x can be given as,

Fig. 13. Curves of Job's method of binary complex show composition of Tb : XO as 1 : 2 at pH 6.4 and λ_{\max} 570 nm.

Fig. 14. Curves of Job's method of ternary complex show composition of Tb : XO : CPB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 6.1 and λ_{\max} 612 nm.

$$x = \frac{-[b_2^2 - b_1^2 + 4(a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)] \pm \sqrt{[b_2^2 - b_1^2 + 4(a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)]^2 - 16(a_1 + b_1)(a_2 + b_2)}}{8[(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)]} \quad \text{(iii)}$$

Values of log K of complexes for Gd^{III} metal ion at pH 6.2 in absence at 570 nm and in presence of CPB at 612 nm; and for Tb^{III} at pH 6.4 in absence at 570 nm and in

presence of CPB at pH 6.1 at 612 nm have been calculated by above method and are summarized in Table 5. These values show that the value for particular metal in presence of CPB is greater than in absence of CPB. This is due to the formation of stable ternary complexes with modified reagent in presence of CPB. The values of composition and stability constant of both the metal ions under study are in well agreement with the results reported earlier²⁻⁵.

Table 5. Composition and stability constants of XO complexes in absence and presence of CPB

Complexes of XO study	pH of study	λ_{\max} of study	Composition A-M : XO : P-M : XO : (CPB) ₂	log K values by Job's method
Gd^{III}	A-6.2	A-570	A-1 : 2	A-5.24
	P-6.2	P-612	P-1 : 2 : 4	P-8.75
Tb^{III}	A-6.4	A-570	A-1 : 2	A-5.32
	P-6.1	P-612	P-1 : 2 : 4	P-8.62

A - Absence and B - Presence of CPB.

Analytical applications of complexes of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} in presence of CPB :

The formation of intense colored ternary complexes in presence of cetylpyridinium bromide with bathochromic shift of about 42 nm for both metal ions and corresponding increase in absorbance values at shifted wavelength facilitates the analytical measurements for microdetermination of metal ions under study. Some important analytical parameters and applications for determination of both metal ions have been summarized in absence and presence of CPB in Table 6.

Rate of color formation and stability of color at room temperature :

Color formation does not depend on reaction time and is almost instantaneous. However the mixtures were kept for 30 min for equilibration before recording their absorbances. Stability of color was tested at room temperature by measuring the absorbance of complex at regular interval of time. Maximum absorbance was achieved in 5 min after the addition of reactants. The color is quite stable for more than 48 h at room temperature. Temperature was found to have no effect on color intensity of ternary complexes from 20-60 °C.

Table 6. Photometric determination of metal ions in absence and presence of cetylpyridinium bromide

Complexes of XO	pH of study	Wavelength of study	Beer's law ranges (ppm)	Effective photometric ranges (ppm)	Molar absorptivities ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)
Gd ^{III}	A-6.2	A-570	A-0.62 – 12.05	A-1.28 – 6.55	A-42400	A-0.0055
	P-6.2	P-612	P-0.50 – 8.58	P-1.01 – 4.03	P-54500	P-0.0040
Tb ^{III}	A-6.4	A-570	A-0.63 – 12.18	A-1.29 – 6.63	A-42500	A-0.0052
	P-6.1	P-612	P-0.51 – 8.72	P-1.08 – 4.09	P-55000	P-0.0049

A – Absence and B – Presence of CPB.

Effect of reagent concentration :

Ten times excess of CPB was added to different volumes of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ of XO solution. The mixture was then kept half an hour for complex formation to observe the complete decolorizing effect. 1 ml of $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ions was then added in each flask and total volume was maintained at 25 ml and adjusted at pH 6.2 for Gd^{III} and 6.1 for Tb^{III} and absorbance readings were recorded at 612 nm for both the metal ions under study. It was found that XO should be present at least two times than metal ion concentration to have maximum color development in presence of CPB. However in absence of CPB, reagent needed was five times as that of metal ion for full color development.

Beer's law and effective photometric ranges :

The linearity between the absorbance of complex and concentration of metal ion was tested by taking the different volumes of metal ion solution of $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ in absence and presence of CPB. The concentration of XO and CPB solutions used were $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively. The volumes of XO and CPB solutions used were 2.0 ml each. Total volume was kept constant at 25 ml at respective pH value for Gd^{III} at pH 6.2 in absence and presence of CPB, for Tb^{III} at pH 6.4 in absence and at pH 6.1 in presence of CPB. The absorbance values were measured at 570 nm in absence and at 612 nm for both the metal ions in presence of CPB.

From a graph of absorbance versus metal ion concentration, the Beer's law ranges were then calculated and found to be 0.6 to 12.11 ppm for binary complexes. However, in presence of CPB, these ranges have been found to be 0.50 to 8.60 ppm for ternary complexes. The most effective photometric ranges as derived from straight line portion of the Ringbom plot²⁵ (i.e. log of metal ion con-

centration versus percentage transmittance) have been found to adhere from 1.28 to 6.60 ppm in absence of CPB. However in presence of CPB, these ranges have been found to be 1.05 to 4.06 ppm. Thus the present values of photometric ranges are in well agreement with the values reported earlier for the metal ions under study^{26,27}. Both the metal ions can be determined by the present proposed method when present in low concentration.

Sensitivities and molar absorptivities :

The average values of molar absorptivities of metal complexes in absence and presence of CPB at the wavelength of study are given in the Table 6. Values clearly indicate the increase in values of the sensitivities and molar absorptivities of ternary complexes in the present investigation, primarily decides the usefulness and importance of the present reactions for the microdetermination. Sandell's sensitivity²⁸ in absence and presence of CPB calculated against absorbance 0.01 unit for both the metal ions under study are shown in Table 6. Thus the present investigation shows sensitization of the reagent in presence of CPB takes place and can be used for the microdetermination of both the metal ions under study.

Effect of foreign ions :

The method suffers from lack of specificity but with less interference. The determination is possible in absence of metal ions such as Be²⁺, Cd²⁺, Fe³⁺, Th⁴⁺, Sc³⁺, Y³⁺, UO₂²⁺, other lanthanides, Ag⁺, Pd²⁺, Hg²⁺, In²⁺, Au³⁺ and anions such as nitrates, oxalates, citrates, succinates and EDTA strongly interfere.

Recommended procedure for microdetermination :

In excess of modified reagent (XO), specific amount (about 50 to 200 μg) of metal ion solution was added. The solution was kept at-least half an hour for complex

formation. By adding distilled water, the solution was adjusted to 25 ml at pH for respective metal ions and kept at standing for half an hour for equilibration. The absorbance of the solution at respective λ_{\max} was measured against reagent blank. The amount of metal ion present in unknown solution can be obtained by comparing this absorbance from the calibration curve obtained under similar condition. The results of ten determination of 126.69 μg per 25 ml for Gd^{III} and 188.41 μg per 25 ml of Tb^{III} showed standard average deviation of 0.022 and 0.032 respectively (Table 7).

Table 7. Determination of individual metal ion in presence of cetylpyridinium bromide

Lanthanide metals	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g}/25$ ml)	Amount found ^a ($\mu\text{g}/25$ ml)	Standard average deviation
Gd^{III}	126.65	126.69	± 0.022
Tb^{III}	188.35	188.41	± 0.032

^aAverage of ten determinations.

Conclusion :

Thus the reagent reported in presence of surfactant CPB can be used as one of the most sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric analysis of Gd^{III} and Tb^{III} when present in extremely small concentration. The increased stability has been achieved in presence of surfactant corresponding to formation of ternary complexation which is adequate for the analytical purposes.

Analytical applications of the ternary complexes i.e. the metallised XO in presence of cationic surfactant CPB highlight the following facts for the sensitive microspectrophotometric determination.

(i) A bathochromic shift in wavelength of absorbance maxima of about 42 nm (average from 570 nm of binary to 612 nm of ternary) has been observed in presence of cationic surfactant CPB. This shifting in λ_{\max} is attributed to the formation of ternary complexes.

(ii) The values of pH range of stability and the optimum pH range of stability show that the greater stability of the ternary complexes in presence of cationic surfactant and has been observed in wider pH range as compared to binary complexes.

(iii) Large bathochromic shift with higher absorbance values at shifted wavelength of the ternary complexes resulted in to heightened molar absorptivity as compared

to binary complexes indicating that the sensitization have been taken place and determination of metal ion can be carried out at lower concentration.

(iv) Values of $\log K$ of complexes for both the metal ions showed that the value for particular metal in presence of CPB is greater than in absence of CPB which is due to the formation of stable ternary complexes with modified reagent in presence of CPB.

(v) From the study of the analytical applications of the ternary complexes, the method has been suggested which appears to be quite sensitive, precise and reproducible. The commercial exploitation of these reactions needs further investigation.

(vi) XO in presence of CPB finds significant applications in spectrophotometric analysis beyond those reported so far. Improved photometric determination may result for many others bivalent and trivalent cations.

Thus the present study suggest really simple and reasonably good method for determination of these metal ions at low concentration by sensitizing the reported reagent XO, using cationic surfactant and estimation can be carried out at simple laboratory with spectrophotometer and pH meter.

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